

SUSTAINABLE BIO-COMPOSITES FOR AUTOMOTIVE INTERIOR PARTS

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1 Introduction

Conventional polymer composites have various advantages, such as lightweight, endurance, flame resistance, low cost, and wide use [1]. Recently, advanced polymer composites containing carbon and glass fibers have been utilized extensively in the aerospace, automotive, and construction industries. [2] Since the matrices and the fiber reinforcements in these advanced composites are based on mineral resources that have long term sustainability have some problems such as accumulating environmental pollution. While recycling may be a viable strategy, the complicated mixed morphology of composite materials makes them inherently difficult to recycle. In comparison, several so called bio-composites, have been developed that offer certain environmental advantages at the end of their use cycle when composites are landfilled or incinerated [3]. For the purposes of this study bio-composites are defined as composite materials that combine natural fibers such as sisal, jute, hemp, and kenaf with either biodegradable or non-biodegradable polymers. Natural fibers have many advantages over synthetic fibers; these advantages include biodegradability, low density, high toughness, acceptable specific strength, reduced dermal and respiratory irritation, low cost, and less use on non-renewable resources. So, if some properties of bio-composites such as low thermal stability in biodegradable matrix polymer and weak interfacial adhesion between matrix and filler are improved, than bio-composites will alternate with conventional advanced polymer composites. Recently, ‘Sick Car Syndrome’ was occurred by the problem for new made cars that have great quantity VOCs (volatile

organic compounds) in their interior parts. Thus, the automotive makers have struggled to reduce emitted VOCs from car interior.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

The Matrix of the bio-composites was poly(lactic acid) (PLA), which was manufactured by Huvis Co., Ltd., South Korea, in the form of fibers with density 1.24 g/cm³, average length of 52 mm. Kenaf fiber was donated by Sutongsang Co., South Korea. Kenaf fiber used in our experiments was bast fibers.

2.2 Sample preparation

The bio-composites of PLA/kenaf fiber were prepared using a carding machine (Kyowa Co. Ltd, Japan). Carding provides a uniform blend of the two fibers [4], this is followed by needle punching, then pre-pressing and finally hot-pressing to form the composite material. The PLA/kenaf non-woven web produced after the carding process was pressed to reduce the thickness of the matt. In the final step, the prepressed matt was hot-pressed for 5 minutes at 200 °C under a pressure of 0.7 MPa (70 kgf/cm²). This process enabled melting of the PLA and good impregnation provided a well consolidated formed sheet. Figure 1 shows the carding process. Headliner and package tray were manufacture by carding process.

Fig. 1. Carding process for PLA/kenaf bio-composites.

2.3 Characterization

Mechanical properties and physical properties of headliner and package tray were conducted. The VOCs emission and formaldehyde were measured 20L small chamber method which is very useful equipment to catch up the sample gas that gas was taken by Tenax-TA after the sample specimens were installed into the dynamic thermal extractor chamber and analyzed by TDS-GC/MSD.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical test of headliner

Fig. 2. Prototype headliner composed of PLA/kenaf fiber bio-composites.

Figure 2 shows the prototype headliner interior part composed of PLA and kenaf fiber by carding process.

Table 1 shows that the test results on the headliner utilizing standard test methods from the automotive industry. These tests were conducted with prototype headliner composed of PLA/kenaf 50 wt%. All test results satisfied the needs for automotive headliner.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of headliner mad of bio-composites

Assessment			Unit	Needs	Result	
Tensile Strength	Normal	lengthwise	kgf/5cm	95	192.7	OK
		widthwise		115	203.9	OK
	Wetproof	lengthwise		85	172.0	OK
		widthwise		110	209.6	OK
Flexural Strength	Normal	lengthwise	kgf/5cm	1.6	3.62	OK
		widthwise		2.8	4.89	OK
	Wetproof	lengthwise		1.5	3.32	OK
		widthwise		2.5	4.70	OK
Dimensional Shrinkage	lengthwise	%	± 1.0	0.46	OK	
	widthwise			0.99	OK	

3.2 VOCs emission of headliner

Table 2 lists the VOCs emission and formaldehyde levels, as detected by TDS-GC/MSD, of various VOCs from the bio-composites. As a result, the VOCs emission levels of PLA/kenaf bio-composites were very low emission levels. And formaldehyde emission levels are also emitted.

Table 2. Formaldehyde and VOCs emission of prototype headliner

VOCs	Limited ^a	Headliner
Formaldehyde	250	219.6
Toluene	1000	4.6
Xylene	870	0
Benzene	30	0
Ethyl benzene	1600	0
Styrene	300	0

^a The standard in Korea.

3.3 VOCs emission of package tray

Table 3 lists the TVOCs emission and formaldehyde levels of prototype package tray, as detected by TDS-GC/MSD, of various VOCs from the bio-composites. As a result, VOCs emission levels are very low. And formaldehyde emission levels are also emitted. So, VOCs and formaldehyde emission levels satisfy with the regulation. Figure 3 shows the prototype package tray.

Fig. 3. Prototype headliner composed of PLA/kenaf fiber bio-composites.

Table 3. Formaldehyde and VOCs emission of prototype package tray

VOCs	Limited ^a	Package tray
Formaldehyde	250	8.9
Toluene	1000	10.5
Xylene	870	Not detected
Benzene	30	Not detected
Ethyl benzene	1600	Not detected
Styrene	300	Not detected

^a The standard in Korea.

3.4 Module for automotive interior part

Interior headliner and package tray modules for an automobile are shown in the photograph of Figure 4 and Figure 5; headliner is the interior ceiling in automobiles and package tray is shelf. The headliner and package module are made of PLA/kenaf 50 wt%.

Fig. 4. Module of headliner made from a 50/50 PLA/kenaf fiber biocomposite.

Fig. 5. Module of package tray made from a 50/50 PLA/kenaf fiber biocomposite.

4 Conclusions

As climate change and resource depletion enter into the broader societal consciousness, there will be an increasing demand for sustainable products based on renewable resources. Here it is demonstrated that long kenaf fibers derived from the bast part of the plant may be used to successfully reinforce PLA; these novel and useful biocomposites are made using a combination of carding and punching processes followed by hot press compression molding.

Over the past several years, many reports in the field of biocomposites filled with natural fibers such as jute, flax, hemp, kenaf and others have been reported. Many researchers are trying to make building interior, electronics, automotive, and other products. To date, few manufactured goods are available in the marketplace. Here we report on a prototype automotive interior part utilizing the formulated biocomposites. And TVOC emission and

formaldehyde emission levels are very low in these results

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